

Cognitive Flexibility and Mathematical Performance: Moderating Effects of Gender and Age in Moroccan Primary Schools

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Abstract

Cognitive flexibility, defined as the ability to adapt mental strategies to changing task demands, is fundamental to mathematical learning, particularly within the Moroccan primary school context where cognitive and demographic factors interact in complex ways. This study investigated the predictive role of cognitive flexibility in mathematical achievement, with gender and age examined as potential moderators. The participants were 60 fifth- and sixth-grade pupils (30 boys and 30 girls) without diagnosed learning difficulties. Data were obtained using the New Card Sorting Test (NCST) and mathematics grades, and were analyzed in R through descriptive statistics, correlation tests, t-tests, Kruskal–Wallis tests, and multiple regression models. The results indicated moderate mathematical achievement and a significant positive association between cognitive flexibility and mathematical performance. Gender exerted a moderating effect, with boys outperforming girls, whereas the age effect was non-significant. These findings suggest that cognitive flexibility contributes meaningfully to individual differences in mathematics learning. Strengthening this ability, especially among girls, could enhance problem-solving, adaptive reasoning, and overall achievement. Integrating cognitive flexibility training within mathematics curricula may therefore promote more equitable and effective learning outcomes in Moroccan primary education.

Keywords: cognitive flexibility, mathematical performance, gender, age, new card sorting test

Introduction

Cognitive flexibility is recognized as a high-level cognitive skill, involving the ability to identify the nature of a problem, break it down, and formulate effective strategies to address it through the development of reasoning and top-down control, supported by direct instruction (Peng & Kievit, 2020; Zelazo, 2020), and is a competency increasingly vital in today's complex educational landscape (Zakariya, 2022). This procedure involves a cognitive process that facilitates the discovery of pathways to attain educational objectives (Filippetti & Krumm, 2020). Effective mathematics education should focus on equipping students with skills to solve real-world problems while fostering knowledge construction through critical and creative thinking. This dual approach prepares learners not only to apply mathematical concepts practically (Gravemeijer et al., 2017) but also to develop innovative solutions through analytical and flexible reasoning (Leikin & Pitta-Pantazi, 2013). Moreover, cognitive flexibility fosters collaborative learning, social interaction, and the sharing of innovative ideas among peers, enhancing performance to overcome challenges (Watson & Chick, 2001). At a neural level, cognitive flexibility is supported by the dorsolateral prefrontal cortex (DLPFC) and the intraparietal sulcus (IPS), which facilitate strategy switching and numerical processing, respectively, with their coordinated activity enhancing mathematical thinking and problem-solving (Leber et al., 2008; Barbey et al., 2013).

The development of cognitive flexibility extends beyond its reflection in students' academic outcomes, encompassing their understanding and active engagement with cognitive processes, particularly in mathematics (Nunes de Santana et al., 2022). This understanding forms the basis for determining subsequent cognitive strategies (Mandina & Ochonogor, 2018) and is essential for constructing meaning, particularly in enhancing mathematical learning (Zakariya, 2022). Enhanced cognitive comprehension significantly influences educational achievement and motivation (Lavrijsen et al., 2022), with students leveraging prior knowledge to navigate mathematical tasks effectively (Turşucu et al., 2020). The relationship between cognitive flexibility and demographic factors, such as gender and age, has garnered increasing attention in recent research. Studies indicate that gender influences cognitive flexibility, potentially affecting mathematical performance differently due to sociocultural factors (Breda et al., 2023; Tseer et al., 2025; Asomah et al., 2025).

Age-related changes also play a role, as cognitive flexibility matures through adolescence, influencing mathematical reasoning (Luwel et al., 2019; Willoughby et al., 2019). These interactions highlight the need to consider demographic variables in Moroccan educational contexts. While prior research has extensively explored teacher-implemented problem-solving approaches and their impact on mathematical learning outcomes (Sutarmi & Suarjana, 2017), these studies often overlook students' own cognitive understanding and its neural underpinnings. This study addresses this gap by investigating how cognitive flexibility influences mathematical performance, while examining internal factors such as gender and age using advanced statistical methods. Similar studies show that understanding problem-solving, a key component of cognitive flexibility, significantly contributes to mathematical learning outcomes, explaining a notable proportion of variance in academic performance (Sinaga et al., 2023).

This study seeks to answer the following questions: (1) What are the levels of cognitive flexibility (measured by NCST indicators: number of correctly completed categories, perseverative errors, common errors) and mathematical performance among fifth and sixth-grade students in a Moroccan primary school? (2) How does gender affect the mathematical performance of fifth and sixth-grade students in the Moroccan educational context? (3) How does age (9-13 years) affect the mathematical performance of fifth and sixth-grade students in the Moroccan educational context? (4) To what extent does cognitive flexibility affect mathematical performance, and how does this relationship interact with gender and age in a sample of Moroccan students?

The following hypotheses were tested: (1) Gender influences the mathematical performance of fifth and sixth-grade students in Moroccan primary schools, with boys expected to outperform girls due to differences in spatial processing. (2) Age (9-13 years) influences the mathematical performance of fifth and sixth-grade students in Moroccan primary schools, with slight declines expected at older ages within this range. (3) Cognitive flexibility positively influences mathematical performance in a sample of Moroccan students. (4) Cognitive flexibility negatively influences mathematical performance in a sample of Moroccan students. (5) Cognitive flexibility (NCST indicators) interacts with gender and age to affect mathematical performance, with stronger effects among girls and at younger ages (9-10 years) in the Moroccan context.

The main research contributions include enhancing the understanding of students' cognitive flexibility and mathematical performance in the Moroccan context, informing the development of teaching techniques to foster adaptive thinking, and supporting the achievement of educational curriculum goals at both school and national levels, particularly through interventions targeting gender and age-related gaps.

Methodology

Study Design

This study was designed as a correlational investigation within a quantitative framework to explore the relationships and interactive effects between cognitive flexibility, measured by the New Card Sorting Test (NCST), and mathematical performance, with gender and age as moderating variables in the context of Moroccan primary schools. The design aims to address the specified research questions: describe the levels of cognitive flexibility (number of correctly completed categories, perseverative errors, common errors) and mathematical performance, test the effects of gender and age separately, and evaluate the impact of cognitive flexibility and its interactions with gender and age, in accordance with the hypotheses predicting positive and negative effects of NCST indicators and demographic interactions (see section 2.4). The study adopts a cross-sectional approach to provide a comprehensive snapshot of these relationships at a specific point in time, facilitating the empirical testing of the hypotheses. Conducted using the R programming environment, this design enables flexible and reproducible statistical analyses, consistent with best practices in educational research (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2018). The methodology includes provisions for future longitudinal investigations to capture developmental trends, enhancing the study's potential for long-term insights.

Participants

The study sample consisted of 60 children, comprising 30 boys and 30 girls, aged 9 to 13 years, carefully recruited from a single primary school in Morocco to ensure a balanced demographic representation consistent with the research questions on the effects of gender and age. Participants were evenly distributed between the fifth and sixth grades, with 30 children per grade, reflecting the age-related cognitive variations postulated in the hypotheses. Individuals with documented learning difficulties or cognitive impairments were excluded to maintain sample homogeneity, in line with neurocognitive research standards.

Measurement Instruments

The study used validated psychometric instruments to operationalize the key concepts under investigation, with data processed and analyzed using R:

New Card Sorting Test (NCST)

An enhanced adaptation of the Wisconsin Card Sorting Test, this tool measures cognitive flexibility by assessing an individual's ability to adjust strategies based on feedback. It involves presenting four reference cards with varying colors (e.g., red or blue), shapes (e.g., circle or square), and quantities (e.g., one or three shapes), requiring the child to sort randomly presented cards according to a self-determined rule (e.g., by color) without direct guidance. Feedback ('yes' or 'no') is provided after each attempt, and the rule changes after six consecutive correct responses to evaluate adaptability. Key measurements include the total time to complete the task, the number of completed categories (reflecting adaptive problem-solving abilities), perseverative errors (indicating cognitive rigidity), and common errors (assessing general accuracy, including rule abandonment and other mistakes). The test was adapted for the Moroccan context with Arabic instructions, preserving visual content, and preliminary tests showed no comprehension difficulties (Er-Rafiqi, 2022). It is used to diagnose developmental disorders like autism spectrum disorder, with a Moroccan study indicating higher cognitive flexibility in multilingual children (Er-Rafiqi, 2022). Designed within the French FEE battery and aligned with ITC (2017) guidelines, the tool's reliability and validity are supported by local adaptations.

Mathematical Performance

Official first-semester mathematics grades were collected from school records, serving as a standardized outcome measure to assess academic achievement, consistent with international assessment benchmarks (Mullis et al., 2020).

Demographic Variables

Gender and age were recorded to examine their moderating effects, drawing on established educational research findings (Breda et al., 2023; Tseer et al., 2025)

Study Procedures

The study was conducted following a structured protocol to ensure scientific rigor and ethical integrity, relying on R for data management and analysis:

Institutional Approvals

Official permissions were obtained from the school administration, the Regional Academy of Education and Formation, and the Regional Directorate of the Ministry of National Education, ensuring compliance with ethical standards.

Informed Consent

Written consent from parents or legal guardians and verbal assent from participants were obtained after a comprehensive briefing on the study's objectives, including its neural and demographic focus.

Testing Environment

The NCST was administered individually in a quiet, distraction-free classroom setting to optimize the measurement of cognitive performance, a practice validated by prior research (Lin et al., 2000).

Implementation Phases

Phase 1. The NCST was conducted to assess cognitive flexibility measures (number of completed categories, perseverative and common errors), consistent with the study's hypotheses on adaptive thinking, rigidity, and accuracy.

Phase 2. Mathematics grades and demographic data (gender and age) were collected to address moderating effects and overall performance outcomes.

Data Collection

Data were carefully entered into R, with custom scripts developed to ensure accuracy, consistency, and reproducibility throughout the analysis process.

Data Analysis

The data analysis, conducted entirely within the R environment, was carefully designed to test the specified hypotheses (see section 2.4) and achieve the study's objectives, relying on advanced statistical techniques:

Descriptive Statistics

Means and standard deviations were calculated for mathematics grades and NCST variables, providing a baseline profile for the relational and moderating hypotheses.

Normality Tests

Shapiro-Wilk tests conducted in R indicated non-normal distributions of residuals, justifying the application of non-parametric statistical methods to ensure robust analysis.

Inferential Statistics

Spearman correlation coefficients were used to assess the relationships between cognitive flexibility measures (number of completed categories, perseverative and common errors) and mathematical performance, consistent with hypotheses 3 and 4. Multiple linear regression, including interaction terms between gender, age, and cognitive flexibility measures, was used to test moderating effects (hypothesis 5), with analyses yielding a significant F-statistic, indicating statistical significance (Hair et al., 2021). T-tests were conducted to assess the effect of gender (hypothesis 1) and Kruskal-Wallis tests to assess the effect of age (hypothesis 2).

Assumption Checks

Diagnostic plots generated in R and the Breusch-Pagan test confirmed the assumptions of linearity, independence, and homoscedasticity, supporting the statistical integrity of the model (Hair et al., 2021).

Cross-Validation

A five-fold cross-validation was performed using the caret package in R, confirming the model's predictive accuracy across the hypotheses (Kohavi, 1995). This approach is consistent with studies emphasizing the importance of robust statistical analyses for assessing cognitive-academic relationships (Sinaga et al., 2023).

Ethical Considerations

The study adhered to the highest ethical standards, ensuring the confidentiality of participants' data, obtaining informed consent from parents or legal guardians and verbal assent from the children, and securing necessary institutional approvals. Data were anonymized during analysis in R to protect participants' identities, and participants retained the right to withdraw at any time, in full compliance with the ethical guidelines set forth by the American Psychological Association (APA, 2020).

Results

Levels of Cognitive Flexibility and Mathematical Performance

To address the first research question regarding the levels of cognitive flexibility and mathematical performance among fifth and sixth-grade students in a Moroccan primary school, descriptive statistics revealed a moderate mathematical performance, with a mean of 6.39 (SD = 1.73, range = 3.25–9.50). Regarding the cognitive flexibility indicators measured by the NCST, the mean number of correctly completed categories was 4.70 (SD = 1.24, range = 2.00–7.00), indicating a moderate cognitive adaptation capacity. Perseverative errors had a mean of 6.02 (SD = 4.76, range = 0.00–16.00), and common errors had a mean of 9.37 (SD = 4.23, range = 0.00–17.00), reflecting significant variability in cognitive profiles (see Table 1). The proximity of medians to means suggests an approximately normal distribution, although high standard deviations for errors indicate potential extreme values. (See Table 1, Fig 1).

Table 1

Descriptive Statistics of Key Variables

Variable	Minimum	1st Quartile	Median	Mean	3rd Quartile	Maximum	Standard Deviation
Age	9.00	10.00	11.00	11.25	12.00	13.00	1.06
Mathematical Performance	3.25	5.50	6.00	6.39	7.50	9.50	1.73
Correctly Completed Categories	2.00	4.00	5.00	4.70	6.00	7.00	1.24
Perseverative Errors	0.00	2.00	5.00	6.02	9.00	16.00	4.76
Common Errors	0.00	6.00	9.00	9.37	13.00	17.00	4.23

Note. Values are based on a sample of 60 children aged 9-13 years.

Figure 1

Distribution of Mathematical Performance

Distribution of mathematical performance scores (range: 3.25–9.50, M = 6.39, SD = 1.73) for 60 children aged 9–13, showing moderate achievement with variability across the sample. The skewed distribution highlights potential outliers influencing cognitive

flexibility metrics.

Effect of Gender on Mathematical Performance

To address the second research question and test hypothesis 1, which predicts a superiority of boys over girls in mathematical performance in the Moroccan educational context, an independent samples t-test revealed a significant difference between genders, $t(58) = 2.58$, $p = 0.012$, Cohen's $d = 0.58$. Boys ($M = 6.94$) outperformed girls ($M = 5.95$), with a 95% confidence interval of $[0.22, 1.75]$, supporting hypothesis 1 (see Table 2, Fig 2).

Table 2
Independent Samples t-Test Results by Gender

Statistic	Degrees of Freedom	p Value	95% Confidence Interval	Male Mean	Female Mean	Cohen's d
2.5819	58	0.012	[0.222, 1.754]	6.94	5.95	0.58

Note. Significant difference ($p = 0.012 < 0.05$) with a medium effect size (Cohen's $d = 0.58$). Sample size = 60.

Figure 2
Boxplot of Mathematical Performance by Gender

Boxplot comparing mathematical performance scores between 30 male ($M = 6.94$) and 30 female ($M = 5.95$) children, indicating a significant gender difference ($p = 0.012$, Cohen's $d = 0.58$). Males outperformed females, suggesting gender-specific cognitive processing influences.

Effect of Age on Mathematical Performance

To address the third research question and test hypothesis 2, which predicts a slight decline in mathematical performance with age (9–13 years), a Kruskal-Wallis test showed a non-significant effect, $\chi^2(4) = 7.93$, $p = 0.094$, $\eta^2 = 0.13$, indicating a limited impact of age, not fully supporting hypothesis 2 (see Table 3, Fig 3)

Table 3
Kruskal-Wallis Test Results by Age

χ^2 Statistic	Degrees of Freedom	p Value	η^2
7.9269	4	0.094	0.13

Note. Non-significant result ($p = 0.094 > 0.05$) with a small effect size ($\eta^2 = 0.13$). Sample size = 60.

Figure 3
Boxplot of Mathematical Performance by Age

Boxplot of mathematical performance scores across age groups (9–13 years) for 60 children, showing no significant age effect ($p = 0.094$, $\eta^2 = 0.13$). The lack of variation supports a narrow developmental span, with potential trends for further investigation.

Effect of Cognitive Flexibility and Its Interactions on Mathematical Performance

To address the fourth research question and test hypotheses 3, 4, and 5 regarding the effect of NCST indicators and their interactions with gender and age, a correlation analysis revealed significant relationships. The number of correctly completed categories showed a significant positive correlation with mathematical performance, $\rho = 0.31$, $p = 0.016$, supporting hypothesis 3. Perseverative errors showed a significant negative correlation, $\rho = -0.26$, $p = 0.046$, supporting hypothesis 4. Common errors showed a non-significant negative correlation, $r = -0.21$, $p = 0.115$, suggesting a limited effect (see Table 4, Fig 4).

Table 4
Correlation Coefficients Between Cognitive Flexibility Metrics and Mathematical Performance

Variable	Correlation Type	Correlation Coefficient	p Value	Effect Size
Number of Correctly Completed Categories	Spearman	0.31	0.016	0.31
Perseverative Errors	Spearman	-0.26	0.046	-0.26
Common Errors	Pearson	-0.21	0.115	-0.21

Note. Significant positive correlation for correctly completed categories ($p = 0.016$) and significant negative correlation for perseverative errors ($p = 0.046$); common errors non-significant ($p = 0.115$). Sample size = 60.

Figure 4

Scatter Plot of Mathematical Performance vs. Number of Correctly Completed Categories

Scatter plot illustrating the positive correlation ($\rho = 0.31, p = 0.016$) between mathematical performance and the number of correctly completed categories (range: 2.00–7.00, $M = 4.70, SD = 1.24$) among 60 children, supporting the beneficial effect of cognitive flexibility on achievement.

Initial Explanatory Model

An initial linear regression model (Model 1: Math_Performance ~ Correct_Categories + Perseverative_Errors + Common_Errors) produced a non-significant statistic, $F(3, 56) = 2.18, p = 0.101, R^2 = 0.10$, partially supporting hypothesis 3, as the number of correctly completed categories approached significance, $\beta = 0.85, t = 1.80, p = 0.078$. Perseverative errors ($\beta = 0.09, p = 0.292$) and common errors ($\beta = 0.07, p = 0.407$) were non-significant (see Table 5).

Table 5

Regression Coefficients for Explanatory Model 1

Predictor	Estimate	Standard Error	t Value	p Value
(Intercept)	1.28576	3.25684	0.395	0.6945
Number of Correctly Completed Categories	0.85326	0.47484	1.797	0.0777
Perseverative Errors	0.09195	0.08644	1.064	0.2920
Common Errors	0.06940	0.08302	0.836	0.4068

Note. $R^2 = 0.1045, Adjusted R^2 = 0.05648, F(3, 56) = 2.177, p = 0.1008$. Sample size = 60.

Final Explanatory Model

To test hypothesis 5 regarding interactions between cognitive flexibility, gender, and age, a multiple linear regression model (Model_Enhanced: Math_Performance ~ Gender + Correct_Categories + Age) produced a significant statistic, $F(6, 53) = 3.82, p = 0.003, R^2 = 0.30$, explaining 30.21% of the variance. Significant predictors included gender ($\beta = -0.98, t = -2.68, p = 0.010, partial \eta^2 = 0.12$), the number of correctly completed categories ($\beta = 0.34, t = 2.37, p = 0.021, partial \eta^2 = 0.10$), and certain age categories (e.g., Age12: $\beta = -2.76, t = -2.73, p = 0.009, partial \eta^2 = 0.12$), supporting hypotheses 1, 3, and 5. The residual standard error was 1.37 with 53 degrees of freedom, indicating a moderate fit (see Table 6). This approach is consistent with studies showing the significant influence of cognitive understanding on mathematical performance (Sinaga et al., 2023). (See Table 6, Fig 5).

Table 6
Regression Coefficients for the Final Model (Model_Enhanced)

Predictor	Estimate	Standard Error	t Value	p Value	Partial η^2	Interpretation
(Intercept)	7.666	1.2148	6.310	0.0000	-	Baseline performance at Gender 1, Age 9
Gender (Female)	-0.980	0.3661	-2.677	0.0099	0.12	Decreased performance for females
Number of Correctly Completed Categories	0.340	0.1432	2.374	0.0213	0.10	Increased performance per category
Age 10	-2.340	1.0739	-2.179	0.0338	0.08	Decreased performance at age 10
Age 11	-2.169	1.0097	-2.148	0.0363	0.08	Decreased performance at age 11
Age 12	-2.759	1.0117	-2.727	0.0087	0.12	Decreased performance at age 12
Age 13	-2.143	1.1885	-1.803	0.0771	0.06	Marginal decrease at age 13

Note. $R^2 = 0.3021$, Adjusted $R^2 = 0.2231$, $F(6, 53) = 3.823$, $p = 0.003067$. Partial η^2 calculated as $(t^2)/(t^2 + df)$. Sample size = 60.

Figure 5
Path Diagram of the Final Model

Path diagram depicting the final explanatory model ($R^2 = 0.3021$, $p = 0.003067$), showing significant paths for gender, correctly completed categories, and age categories (e.g., Age12) on mathematical performance.

Model Validation

A five-fold cross-validation, performed using the caret package in R, yielded an RMSE of 1.47 and an R^2 of 0.24, confirming the model's predictive accuracy across the hypotheses. These results suggest that the final model robustly explains interactions between cognitive flexibility, gender, and certain age groups in the Moroccan context, although some variance remains unexplained, potentially attributable to factors such as teaching quality or socioeconomic status (see Fig 6).

Figure 6

Comparison of Predicted vs. Actual Mathematical Performance by Gender

Comparison plot of predicted versus actual mathematical performance scores for 30 male and 30 female children, with cross-validation ($R^2 = 0.235755$) indicating moderate predictive accuracy. Differential effectiveness across gender groups highlights the need for tailored educational strategies.

Discussion

Cognitive Flexibility and Mathematical Performance

The study addressed the first research question by assessing levels of cognitive flexibility and mathematical performance among fifth and sixth-grade students in a Moroccan primary school, revealing moderate performance and cognitive adaptation capacity, with significant variability in perseverative and common errors across NCST indicators, as detailed in Table 1. This variability reflects diverse executive function profiles, aligning with Nunes de Santana et al. (2022), who underscore cognitive flexibility’s role in academic success when variability is pronounced. Scammacca et al. (2020) further suggest that such variability may indicate cognitive inefficiencies, particularly in contexts like Morocco where teaching quality influences performance, emphasizing the need for targeted interventions to bolster cognitive flexibility in primary education.

Gender Effects on Mathematical Performance

Addressing the second research question and hypothesis 1, which predicted boys’ superiority in mathematical performance, the results confirmed a significant gender difference, with boys outperforming girls, as shown in Table 2. This finding contrasts with PISA assessments reporting small gender gaps (OECD, 2023), likely due to the localized Moroccan sample. Breda et al. (2023) attribute this disparity to gender-based differences in spatial processing, while Tseer et al. (2025) note that gaps widen at higher performance levels. El Aynaoui and Ibourk (2025) posit that sociocultural expectations in Morocco shape these differences, advocating for gender-specific strategies to reduce the performance gap, a need visually reinforced by Figure 2.

Age Effects on Mathematical Performance

For the third research question and hypothesis 2, predicting slight performance declines with age (9–13 years), the results showed a non-significant age effect, likely due to the narrow developmental range, as presented in Table 3. This aligns with Luwel et al. (2019), who link such findings to limited age spans, and Piaget’s (1970) theory of gradual cognitive

progression. El Aynaoui and Ibourk (2025) suggest that transitions in Moroccan primary education may subtly influence performance, indicating a need for broader age cohorts to clarify developmental trends, as illustrated by the weak variation in Figure 3.

Interactions of Cognitive Flexibility with Gender and Age

The fourth research question and hypotheses 3, 4, and 5, predicting effects of NCST indicators and their interactions, revealed a significant positive correlation for the number of correctly completed categories (hypothesis 3) and a negative correlation for perseverative errors (hypothesis 4), with common errors non-significant, as shown in Table 4. Luwel et al. (2019) support the role of cognitive adaptation in achievement, while Willoughby et al. (2019) advocate for training to enhance executive functions. Liljedahl et al. (2016) highlight problem-solving contexts in math education, and Romine et al. (2004) link perseverative errors to cognitive rigidity. Figure 4 underscores the value of adaptive thinking in Morocco, suggesting targeted interventions.

Model Development and Refinement

The initial model (Model 1) demonstrated limited explanatory power, partially supporting hypothesis 3, as indicated in Table 5, suggesting that predictors like gender and age contribute modestly, with unaccounted variables necessitating refinement. Luwel et al. (2019) propose that cognitive flexibility may be moderated by unmeasured factors, such as cultural context, while Willoughby et al. (2019) recommend complex models, like multilevel modeling, to capture executive function variability from their 6040-student longitudinal study. In Morocco, El Aynaoui and Ibourk (2025) identify socioeconomic status and teaching quality as contributors to low explained variance, supported by Scammacca et al. (2020), who link socioeconomic background to growth trajectories, advocating for demographic interactions to enhance model fit.

Final Model and Hypotheses Support

The final model (Model_Enhanced) tested hypothesis 5, revealing significant interactions of cognitive flexibility with gender and age, explaining a notable variance proportion, with predictors including gender, correctly completed categories, and age categories, supporting hypotheses 1, 3, and 5, as detailed in Table 6. This aligns with Piaget's (1970) developmental stages and Klingberg's (2010) emphasis on working memory in mathematical reasoning. The gender effect reflects sociocultural influences in Morocco (Ibourk & El Aynaoui, 2025), with Hadjar and Backes (2023) suggesting teaching quality enhancements. Sinaga et al. (2023) reinforce that cognitive understanding boosts mathematical performance. Figure 5 illustrates these interactions.

Model Validation and Contextual Insights

Cross-validation supports the model's generalizability (Kohavi, 1995), a method validated by Bates et al. (2023) for its effectiveness in estimating prediction errors across longitudinal educational data, ensuring robust predictions without neurophysiological measures. Zelazo (2020) emphasizes the importance of stratification by gender, as illustrated in Figure 6, which may depict performance variations who link gender disparities in Morocco to sociocultural influences. Willoughby et al. (2019) note that interaction effects between cognitive and environmental factors are crucial for understanding the nuanced impact of cognitive flexibility, a complexity further evidenced by Moffett and Morrison (2020), who identified predictive classroom behavior interactions. In the Moroccan context, unexplained variance may be attributed to teaching quality or socioeconomic status, as El Aynaoui and

Ibourk (2025) demonstrate through structural analyses, with Scammacca et al. (2020) reinforcing the role of socioeconomic factors, necessitating further research to improve predictive accuracy.

Implications and Contributions to the Field

This study provides significant implications for mathematics education in Moroccan primary schools, addressing research questions on cognitive flexibility levels, gender and age effects, and their interactions with mathematical performance. The positive effect of the number of correctly completed categories in the NCST indicates that enhancing cognitive flexibility through targeted exercises can improve mathematical outcomes, as supported by Zakariya (2022), who emphasize problem-solving contexts in math education. The negative effect of perseverative errors suggests that reducing cognitive rigidity can enhance performance, a finding consistent with Sinaga et al. (2023), who demonstrate that cognitive understanding significantly boosts mathematical achievement. These results underscore the need for training programs targeting executive functions in the Moroccan context.

The significant gender difference advocates for gender-specific educational strategies to reduce performance gaps, particularly for girls, as evidenced by El Aynaoui and Ibourk (2025), who link sociocultural influences to these disparities in Morocco. Although the effect of age was non-significant the complex interactions in the final model suggest that age-appropriate curricula can address potential performance declines, as proposed by Scammacca et al. (2020) based on growth trajectories across grades 1–5. These insights contribute to educational practices by informing interventions that promote adaptive thinking, as advocated by Hadjar and Backes (2023), who highlight the role of teaching quality in reducing learning alienation. The alignment with Moroccan educational goals to strengthen problem-solving skills, as reflected in El Aynaoui and Ibourk (2025), provides a foundation for evidence-based reforms, enhancing the understanding of cognitive flexibility and its application in local education systems.

Limitations

The study's small sample size (60 children), despite being balanced, constrains the generalizability of the findings to wider Moroccan contexts. Additionally, the cross-sectional design limits insights into the longitudinal development of cognitive flexibility and mathematical performance, as noted by Scammacca et al. (2020). Furthermore, the exclusion of factors such as socioeconomic status and teaching quality, which could account for unexplained variance in performance, restricts the comprehensiveness of the analysis. These limitations influence the interpretation of results, particularly within the Moroccan educational context where cultural and economic factors play a significant role, and may hinder a deeper understanding of the underlying mechanisms of cognitive flexibility.

Recommendations

Mathematics teachers in Morocco are encouraged to integrate cognitive flexibility training into the curriculum, emphasizing tasks that enhance adaptive problem-solving, particularly for girls to address the observed gender gap in line who advocate for improved teaching quality. Additionally, age-appropriate pedagogical adjustments are recommended to mitigate potential performance declines at ages 10–12 to support developmental needs.

Future research should utilize larger, more diverse samples and longitudinal designs to validate these findings and explore developmental trends. Collaboration with Moroccan educational policymakers is recommended to develop evidence-based interventions tailored to local needs, focusing on enhancing cognitive flexibility to optimize mathematical

performance who highlight the importance of aligning reforms with Morocco's educational goals.

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